

Synthesis, characterization and spectral studies of copper(II) complexes of *o*-ethyl and *o*-*t*-butylesters of hydrazine carboxylic acid

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Abstract : New copper(II) complexes of the general composition CuL_2X_2 (where L = *o*-ethyl and *o*-*t*-butylesters of hydrazine carboxylic acid, X = Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , NCS^-) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, IR) and magnetic studies. All the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature except $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{SO}_4]$ which is bi-bielectrolyte as revealed by their molar conductance data in nitrobenzene.

Keywords : Copper(II) complex, hydrazine carboxylic acid, spectral studies.

Hydrazine carboxylic acid having four donor sites, is known to behave as a bidentate ligand and form complexes with non-transition and transition metal ions^{1,2}. The ligating property of hydrazine carboxylic acid is expected to be modified by the replacement of hydrogen atom of the acidic group with alkyl groups, which may possibly lead to metal complexes of different stereochemistries, depending upon the nature of the substituents. It was interesting to investigate structure of the complexes formed by the interaction of copper(II) salts with *o*-ethylester of hydrazine carboxylic acid and *o*-*t*-butylester of hydrazine carboxylic acid.

Structure of ligand (R = C₂H₅, t-C₄H₉)

Results and discussion

Results of elemental analysis and conductivity data of complexes are given in Table 1. The magnetic moment values are given in Table 2 and are close to 1.9 B.M. This indicates the presence of a single electron on copper(II) in these complexes but yield no stereochemical information³. It is apparent that the coordination of amines lowers the N-H stretching frequency by about 100 cm⁻¹. It has been proposed⁶ that this lowering of N-H stretch-

ing frequency upon coordination is due to the drainage of electrons from the nitrogen atom to the metal ion which in turn weakens the N-H bond.

The electronic spectral data of all the copper(II) complexes are reported in Table 3. An inspection of the electronic spectra of these complexes immediately rules out the possibility of tetrahedral structure since no major spectral band is observed below 10000 cm⁻¹^{4,5}. None of these compounds appears to be penta-coordinated.

The NH₂ bending deformation vibration has been assigned to the band observed at about 1600 cm⁻¹ in the complexes as well as in the ligands⁷. In an un-ionised carboxylate group, the carbonyl (C=O) stretching vibration appears at about 1700 cm⁻¹⁸. In salts of carboxylic acids the characteristic carbonyl absorption band is replaced by two bands in the region 1620-1560 and 1400-1300 cm⁻¹, assigned to anti-symmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations respectively.

Raman data^{9,10} on a number of carboxylic acids indicate that the salt formation results in the disappearance of normal carbonyl stretching absorption and its replacement by a band near 1430 cm⁻¹. Thus symmetric (COO⁻) carboxylate stretching vibration appears at 1575 cm⁻¹ in acetate ion. The anti-symmetric stretching vibration of a carboxylate group is known to be particularly sensitive to the mode of coordination. As the covalent character of M-O bond increases, the anti-symmetric stretching fre-

Table 1. Analytical data on copper(II) complexes of *o*-ethylester and *o*-*t*-butylester of hydrazine carboxylic acid

Complexes	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Conductivity Λ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		Cu	C	H	N	Anion	
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Blue	14.23 (14.57)	17.87 (18.09)	4.90 (5.02)	14.88 (15.05)	23.85 (24.15)	27
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ Cl ₂]	Green	19.45 (18.95)	20.95 (21.05)	4.68 (4.64)	16.47 (16.37)	21.05 (20.75)	4.5
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ Br ₂]	Spike green	14.73 (14.62)	16.56 (16.70)	3.80 (3.71)	13.11 (12.99)	37.82 (37.73)	5.2
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Green	16.65 (16.48)	24.76 (24.80)	4.23 (4.13)	23.25 (21.70)	31.00 (29.98)	6.1
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ Cl ₂]	Green	15.75 (15.83)	30.00 (30.15)	5.95 (6.03)	13.95 (14.07)	17.62 (17.84)	3.8
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ Br ₂]	Green	12.89 (12.94)	24.58 (24.64)	4.81 (4.93)	11.36 (11.45)	32.70 (32.86)	4.1
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Blue	13.81 (13.90)	26.48 (26.60)	5.21 (5.32)	18.43 (18.62)	- -	3.9
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Green	13.42 (13.55)	32.76 (32.96)	5.31 (5.48)	18.91 (19.18)	26.13 (26.48)	5.8

Table 2. Magnetic properties of copper(II) complexes of *o*-ethylester and *o*-*t*-butylester of hydrazine carboxylic acid

Complexes	χ_g $\times 10^6$	Temp. ($T + 273$) K	χ_M $\times 10^6$	χ_M $\times 10^6$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ Cl ₂]	3.46	303	1186.11	1341.47	1.81
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ Br ₂]	1.93	303	826.37	1001.47	1.90
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂]SO ₄	2.31	303	847.71	1001.43	1.87
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	2.06	304	827.13	1001.51	1.92
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	2.15	303	850.35	1001.37	1.83
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	2.51	304	974.32	1139.67	1.85
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ Cl ₂]	1.97	303	786.94	1001.46	1.89
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ Br ₂]	1.59	303	778.95	1001.47	1.90
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	1.77	303	802.98	1001.44	1.88
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	3.18	303	1393.42	1416.10	1.86

quency also increases. Our results are consistent with the results reported earlier¹¹⁻¹⁴. Thus the overall evidence available from the above investigations indicate that the complexes approximate to D_{4h} symmetry, the bond formation taking place between metal ion and amino nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen atoms.

Experimental

o-Ethyl and *o*-*t*-butylesters of hydrazine carboxylic acid were procured from Fluka, A.G., Germany and were used as such. Copper(II) salts of AnalaR grade were used.

Synthesis of complexes : 1.0 mmol CuX₂ (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, NCS⁻) solution was added dropwise to an alcoholic solution of the ligand (L) (L = H₂NH.NHCOOC₂H₅, H₂NH.NHCOOC₄H₉) (3.0 mmol) with constant stirring. It is further stirred for 2-3 h and kept overnight. A coloured complex was precipitated. It was washed with dry diethylether (2-3 ml, 2-3 times) to remove excess of ligand and dried over P₄O₁₀.

For bromo complexes 2.0 g of potassium bromide was dissolved in 15-20 ml ethanol and was mixed (1.0 mmol) with copper(II) chloride dissolved in 5-6 ml alco-

Table 3. Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) of copper(II) complexes with *o*-ethylester and *o*-*t*-butylester of hydrazine carboxylic acid and calculated ligand field parameters

Complexes	Observed bands (cm^{-1}) and calculated parameters			10Dq
	(d-d bands)	Charge transfer bands		
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ Cl ₂]	16949 (broad)	24038	28735	8475
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ Br ₂]	18382 17241 16556	24630	28089	9824
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	16691	23809 25641	29411	8716
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	17126	24139	28635	8563
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ Cl ₂]	17605 (broad)	25510	27173	8802
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ Br ₂]	17435	25438	27849	8717
[Cu(H ₂ N.NHCOOC ₄ H ₉) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	17590	25315	27642	8795

hol and the entire solution was stirred for about one hour over a magnetic stirrer. It was further concentrated to one third of its volume on a water bath. On cooling, white crystals of potassium chloride were separated out and filtered off.

For thiocyanato complexes a solution of AnalaR copper(II) chloride (4 g; 10 ml ethanol) was mixed with a solution of ammonium thiocyanate (12 g; 15–20 ml alcohol) and concentrated to half of its volume on a water bath. On cooling a fine white precipitate of ammonium chloride was obtained, it was filtered off and the filtrate containing copper(II) thiocyanate was stirred with (3.0 mmol) ethanolic solution of ligand for about 3 h. A green coloured compound was obtained which was washed successively with small fraction of ether and dried as usual.

Bis-(o-ethylhydrazinecarboxylato)diaquocopper(II) sulphate, [Cu(H₂N.NHCOOC₂H₅)₂(H₂O)₂]SO₄: 10 ml (1.0 mmol) aqueous solution of copper sulphate pentahydrate was stirred with 20 ml (3.0 mmol) ethanolic solution of ligand for about 30 min, and kept overnight; on further concentration, a blue crystalline complex was obtained, washed with ether and was dried over P₄O₁₀ in a vacuum desiccator.

Routine analyses were carried out in our laboratory.

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References

1. A. Braibanti *et al.*, *Nature*, 1966, **211**, 1174.
2. A. Braibanti, F. Dallavalle, M. A. Pellinghelli and F. Laporati, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1430.
3. B. J. H. Hathaway and D. E. Billing, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **5**, 162.
4. L. W. Lawe and L. T. Taylor, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 295.
5. R. N. Patel, N. Singh and V. L. N. Gundla, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, **45**, 614.
6. R. N. Patel, N. Singh and V. L. N. Gundla, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 6169.
7. N. Sravanam, B. N. Sivasankar, R. Govind and K. K. M. Yusuff, *Synthesis React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1994, **24**, 703.
8. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methun, London, 1964.
9. J. Fujita, K. Nakamoto and Kobayashi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 1014.
10. J. Fujita, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **36**, 324.
11. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds", Part-B, 5th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1997.
12. B. P. Baranwal, A. K. Singh, T. Fatma and T. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, **45**, 2006.
13. G. B. Deacon and R. J. Phillips, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **33**, 1227.
14. G. Mathew, M. S. Suseela and R. Krishanan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, **45**, 2040.